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Scaling up of extractor-free electrosprays in linear arrays

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Abstract

Electrospray offers unique atomization of liquids, whereby micro- or nano-droplets with very narrow size distributions are generated from electrified Taylor cones. To scale up this process, many electrospray emitters must be operated simultaneously, while the flow rate per emitter must remain low to preserve stability. To cope with the electrostatic repulsion between the various elements in the system, it is common to position the emitters very near a counter-electrode. Instead, we have studied the conditions leading to robust scalable spraying by using linear arrays of electrosprays in which the counter-electrode is far compared to the inter-emitter separation. In our design, a row of emitter tubes protrudes out of a backplate, and the counter-electrode is a flat collector plate set at a high negative electric potential. In addition, electrodes at both ends of the array enable uniform electrical field conditions, while preventing electrical gaseous discharges. Strong electrostatic interactions are expected between the spray plumes and the Taylor cones. Nonetheless, we show that this geometry is scalable without bound, both by electric field computations, as by experiments performed under different geometrical configurations, liquid flow rates per emitter, and electrical conductivities of the liquid (mainly, NaCl/MEG solutions). The onset voltage required to stabilize the spraying at all emitter positions approaches a plateau as the number of operated emitters increases. Eventually, at high enough potential difference, the cones and sprays misalign, pointing in directions in consonance with minute zig-zag misalignments of the emitters, revealing the importance of small imbalances in the electrostatic forces at the Taylor cones.

Keywords:

aerosol, electrohydrodynamic atomization, electrospray, electrostatic spraying, multiplexing, space charge

1 Introduction

Electrospray, also known as *electrohydrodynamic atomization* (EHDA) or *electrohydrodynamic spraying*, is an unparalleled liquid atomization process, whose scaling up remains a challenge. It is based on the stabilization of a liquid jet at the end of an electrified conical meniscus (called Taylor cone) produced by the action of an intense electric field. This jet often undergoes periodic capillary breakup, releasing uniformly sized droplets (Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018). Electrospray can produce dense sprays of quasi size-monodisperse droplets, over a wide droplet size range from microns to nanometers. These droplets have been used for making engineered nano/micro-sized particles with extremely narrow size distributions, or thin films, out of a wide range of materials present in the droplets (Jaworek et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2012). In addition, it is possible to engineer particles with complex internal composition (e.g. core-shell or multilayered microparticles) by merging two or more liquid streams of suitable chemical compositions within the same Taylor cone (e.g. coaxially) (Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018; Mehta et al., 2017; Yan et al., 2017; Xie et al., 2015).

However, the scaling up of electrospray is not trivial, as it involves operating multiple Taylor cones in a small space in the presence of strong electrostatic fields. The liquid rate passing through a single Taylor cone is constrained because stabilizing the cone and its jet relies on delicate balances between forces (e.g. interfacial electric and surface tension stresses) (Gañán-Calvo et al., 2018). For example, to produce micrometer-radius droplets requires a volumetric rate typically of $\sim 10^{-11}$ m³/s. Such small rates suffice for analytical chemistry applications of electrospray, namely *electrospray ionization mass spectrometry* or ESI-MS (Fenn, 2003), as a source of particles for calibration of aerosol instruments (Hogrefe et al., 2004; Steiner et al., 2017), or other lab scale experimentation. However, obviously, such low rates do not suffice to meet industrial demands of potential applications.

At lab scale, electrospray arrays have been implemented in virtually every application of electrospray: Pharmaceutical particle synthesis (Almería et al., 2010, 2011; Kawakami, 2012), surface coating (Tang & Gomez, 2015), micro-electronics cooling (Deng & Gomez, 2011), mass spectrometry in nanospray mode (Kelly et al., 2007, 2008a; Mao et al., 2011), microprotein arrays (Bhatnagar, 2007), 3D printing (Wang et al., 2015), micro-combustion (Kyritsis et al., 2004; Deng, Klemic et al., 2007), colloidal spacecraft propulsion (Velásquez-García et al., 2006; Krpoun & Shea, 2009), and nanofiber production by electrospinning (Zhou et al., 2009). Studied geometries include 2D square and hexagonal patterns, and 1D linear and circular ones (Lhernould et al., 2011). Clearly, 2D arrays can accommodate greater emitter density than 1-D geometries, and their scale up to produce core-shell nanoparticles is a promising area of research (Olvera-Trejo & Velásquez-García, 2016). Yet, 1D arrays can be convenient to use when emitter density needs not be extremely high. In addition, drying of the droplets for producing particles is straightforward in 1D electrospray arrays.

Despite considerable progress in this area, system reliability remains challenging. The multiplexing of electrospays is dependent on attaining similar electric field at all Taylor cones' positions in the array. This has often been achieved by means of the so-called *extractor electrode*, a perforated plate or a ring which is positioned near each Taylor cone and is set to a different voltage. As the droplets pass through an aperture on the extractor electrode, they become attracted to a downstream electrode held at a suitable potential. By keeping a small separation between Taylor cones and the extractor electrode, the cones become electrostatically shielded from one another as well as from the spray charge (Bocanegra et al., 2005; Deng et al., 2006, 2009; Almería et al., 2010). The extractor electrode solution, however, is not without issues, especially when used at atmospheric pressure with 2D arrays and very small droplets (Bocanegra et al. 2005; Deng & Gomez, 2007; Deng et al., 2009; Higuera 2013; Kempen et al., 2016).

On the other hand, in dense 1D arrays the electrostatic interactions among emitters are significantly reduced, as well as between the emitters and the sprays, compared to 2D arrays with similar inter-emitter spacing. Hence, in this research we ask whether robust operation of dense 1D arrays is possible *without* assistance of an extractor electrode. As listed in Table 1 all previous designs of 1D linear arrays either contain extractor electrodes or the counter-electrode is located very near the Taylor cones (about 1-2 times the inter-emitter separation, called "pitch"). The only reported cases with 1D arrays in which the separation between emitters and counter-electrode was large compared to the emitters' pitch had a pitch of many millimeters; therefore, we do not consider such arrays to be "dense" here (Almekinders & Jones, 1999; Kawakami, 2012). Therefore, in the present study we have considered 1D linear array designs *without* an extractor electrode, wherein the droplet collection electrode is at a large distance compared to the emitters' pitch. In addition, our capillary tube emitters protrude out of a backplate, set parallel to the collection plate.

Specifically, in this work we have addressed the question of whether such "linearly dense" arrays of Taylor cones are up-scalable without bound, by studying how the onset voltage scales with the number of operated (spraying) emitters. Since the counter-electrode sits far from the Taylor cones, strong electrostatic interactions between the cones are expected, resulting in non-uniform electrostatic field. To offset this issue, several studies (Rulison & Flagan, 1993; Hubacz & Marijnissen, 2003; Quang Tran et al., 2010) have used passive (non-spraying) electrodes at the edges of the array (usually, dummy nozzles), a strategy also used on 2D arrays by Deng et al., 2006. However, this design seems too restrictive so here we have improved such previous designs to obtain robust stability. Another goal of the present work is to report on symmetry breaking of the electrospays which develops as the applied voltage becomes large enough.

Table 1 – Prior studies using 1D-linear electrospray emitter arrays (with > 5 emitters; atmospheric pressure)^{1,2}

References (in chronological order)	Kind of study, application	Emitters type	Emitters number x inter-emitter separation (pitch)	Extractor plate?	Emitter - counter-electrode ³ separation	End-electrodes?	Droplet diameter range (µm)
Rulison & Flagan (1993)	Parametric study on array operation	Metal capillary tubes, plus 1 dummy one at each array end	6 x several pitches	No	Not reported	Yes	N.A.
Almekinders & Jones (1999)	Technical note	Sawtooth ("serrations")	24 x 6.5 mm	No	Large (>> 1 cm)	No	112-260 VMD
Kelly et al. (2007, 2008a)	LC / nanoESI-MS	Pulled fused-silica capillaries	19 x 0.5 mm 9 x 1 mm	No	1 mm 1 – 1.5 mm	No	N.A. (< 1, probably)
Kim et al. (2007)	Lab-on-a-chip / nanoESI-MS	Monolithic silica emitters protruding from Si wafer	10 x 0.010 mm	Yes	Not reported (not used)	No	N.A.
Wang et al. (2007)	Biomolecules pulsed deposition	Silica in MEMS device (10 µm emitter diameter)	10 x 0.2 mm	No	0.2 mm	No	N.A.
Quang Tran et al. (2010)	Operation and design	Tubes milled on PMMA	10 x 2 mm	Yes	4 mm	No	N.A.
Mao et al. (2011)	nanoES – MS	Linear Monolithic silica emitters	10 x 0.040 mm	No	Not reported	No	N.A.
Lhernould et al. (2011)	Operation and design	PC slab with holes (I.D. 0.15 mm)	8 x 2 mm	Yes	0.8 mm	No	N.A.
Kawakami (2012)	Pharma particles production	Stainless-steel needles (1 mm diameter)	8 x 10 mm	No	150 mm	No	N.A.
Lojewski et al. (2013)	Operation and design	Tubes milled on brass and on PC	51 x 0.5 mm	Yes	Not reported	No	6.5 – 12 d ₁₀
Kim & Kim (2014)	Operation and design	Sawtooth, plus 2 dummy teeth at each end	10 x 8 mm	No	10 mm	Yes	16 – 21 d ₁₀
Kumar et al. (2017)	Parametric study on array operation	Stainless-steel emitters (0.2 mm I.D.)	5 x 1.5 mm	No	2.5 mm	No	N.A.
Zhao et al. (2017)	Technical note	Sawtooth, cut from paper	9 x 3 mm	No	About 5 mm	No	6.9 d ₁₀

¹We have considered only arrays with more than 5 emitters.²Abbreviations: LC = liquid chromatography; MS = mass spectrometry; N.A.= not available; nanESI = nano-electrospray ionization; PC = polycarbonate; PDMS = poly(dimethyl siloxane); PMMA = poly(methyl methacrylate); VMD = volume median diameter³The counter electrode is the extractor electrode, if one is present. It is the mass spectrometer inlet, if one is used.

For the experimental work, we have used a common solvent, ethylene glycol (MEG), mixed with electrolytes. This study includes the following factors: the number of operated emitters, the separation between the collector and backplate, and the liquid volumetric flow rate. A novel method used in this study is the continuous recording of the current-time traces emitted by each Taylor cone, individually, which allows monitoring the stability of the spraying. The experimental methodology has been complemented with numerical solutions of the electric field.

In the present study we have decided to use solutions based on MEG for three reasons: 1) Owing to their relatively large surface tension of this solvent, such solutions do not wet the sides of the stainless-steel emitters; 2) MEG has a low vapor pressure at ambient temperature, and 3) its relatively high polarity allows to cover a wide range of electrical conductivities, including values appropriate to obtain droplets' diameters of order 1 μm . The conclusions from this study can be extrapolated to other solvents and solutions, so long as precautions are taken to minimize wetting and solvent evaporation. We discuss the importance of controlling wetting in section 3.2. Regarding solvent evaporation, low boiling point solvents (like dichloromethane, acetone, chloroform, etc) are often used to solubilize polymers (Bodnár et al., 2018; Xie et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2012; Peltonen et al., 2010). In these cases, solvent evaporation must be controlled (or minimized) when using electrospray for particle production. Another known problem is moisture absorption at the Taylor cone when water acts as a non-solvent, causing solute precipitation (Bodnár et al., 2018). Evaporation and non-solvent induced phase separation triggered by ambient humidity can be avoided by enclosing the spraying in a dry chamber, or by means of a gentle gas flow around the Taylor cone containing enough solvent vapor to prevent or reduce solvent evaporation from the cone (Bodnár & Rosell-Llompart, 2013; Larsen et al., 2004).

2 Experimental methodology

2.1 Materials

All reagents were used as purchased, without further purification. Sodium chloride (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99\%$, AR grade) was dissolved in ethylene glycol (MEG, Scharlau, Reagent grade) at various concentrations using a magnetic stirrer (Table 2). Acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, glacial) was mixed with H_2O prior to mixing with ethylene glycol. All solutions were prepared at room temperature, and their compositions and electrical conductivities are shown in Table 2. These conductivities are consistent with extrapolated values from data reported by Sandengen & Kaasa (2006). The other solution properties of relevance do not differ much from the pure solvent values, as the most concentrated of our solutions, SC900, has solute molar fraction of only 9.5×10^{-4} (and no significant solvent evaporation is expected). For easy reference, the properties of MEG (20 $^\circ\text{C}$) are listed here (Tsierkezos & Molinou, 1998, Riddick et al., 1986): Surface tension, 48.4 mN/m; dielectric constant, 38.7; density, $1.11 \times 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (20 to 30

°C); viscosity, 20.8 mPa·s. This surface tension is consistent with values obtained for our solutions using the pendant drop method *in situ* before spraying. ImageJ plugin pendent_drop-2.0.4 was used to analyze the images (Daerr & Mogné, 2016). The solution values ranged from 47.4 mN/m (for SC027) to only 51.8 mN/m (for SC900). These differences could be errors of the method or could be due to moisture absorption; however, this effect would be expected to be much smaller on the Taylor cones, as they have smaller interfacial area.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the setup.

2.2 Electro spray generation setup

The schematic of the setup is shown in Fig. 1. A solution is loaded into the liquid reservoirs from which it is supplied to the electro spray emitters when the reservoirs are gas-pressurized. Each reservoir (tuberculin 1.0 mL Henke Sass Wort NORM-JECT syringes without plunger) is vertically positioned and is connected to a 27-gauge \times $\frac{1}{2}$ " hypodermic needle fitted to a capillary PTFE line (Teknokroma, 360 μ m I.D., 580 μ m, 550 mm length) which leads to an electro spray emitter tube. To achieve independent control of the liquid supply rate and the applied voltage, in each line we have inserted a short section of fused silica tubing (100 μ m I.D., 100 mm length) which elevates the hydrodynamic resistance such that the reservoir gauge pressure exceeded 1 psi. This value greatly exceeds the Laplace pressure at the emitter exit; which is the surface tension coefficient over emitter outer radius γ/R (0.015 psi for ethylene glycol). The pressure was measured with a digital manometer and the flow rate were computed from flow rate versus gauge pressure calibrations performed with zero applied voltage.

The electro spray emitters are 100 mm long sections of 304 stainless-steel capillary tubing (Tubos Capilares, Spain; O.D. 400 μ m, I.D. 160 μ m) square-cut and polished on their exit end. They protrude out of the *backplate*, which is a perforated metal plate held parallel to the collector plate. The support structure rests on the collector *plate* with four Delrin[®] legs which sit on insulating spacers used for controlling height (not shown). Initially a rectangular brass plate was used as collector. Later on, we added a stainless-steel perforated metal plate on top of the collector plate, with absorbent paper sandwiched between the two, to prevent puddle formation due to liquid accumulation. The collector plate and backplate are sized 85 x 235 mm, defining a parallel-capacitor in which the emitters and the electro sprays are shielded from external electrical conditions and perturbations. The emitters are sandwiched in a sub-assembly consisting of two Delrin[®] mirror blocks with pre-cut grooves, press fit together by two screws (not shown). Additional electrodes are placed at the ends of the array, as described later (sec. 3.2). For the 11 emitters at 2.5 mm pitch, the standard deviation for the emitter separations (along the array or x-axis) is only 0.09 mm, and that for the cross-array (y-axis) displacements from a perfect line is only 0.06 mm.

The electric field necessary for electro spraying is provided by a negative high voltage (*HV*) power supply connected (Ultravolt, HV-RACK-4-250-0032, 0 to -15 kV range) to the collector through a high voltage-rated 250 M Ω safety-resistor. We continuously monitor the applied electric potential at the collector V_C by means of a HV probe (Testec, TT-HVP-40, $10^9 \Omega$), as shown in Fig. 1. The emitters and the backplate are earth-grounded through nanoammeters of homemade design (based on op-amp current-to-voltage converter design) housed in a shielded box. The output voltages from the nanoammeters, digital manometer, and high voltage probe are fed to a National instruments PCI 6221 DAQ card on a desktop computer. Fig. 2 shows example traces for a typical run in which the collector voltage was adjusted manually at a constant vial pressure (thus steady liquid supply), starting with zero voltage. The current traces show steps when the spraying transitions from one mode to another. In addition, the current is a

monotonous function of flow rate. Therefore, differences in current can be used to detect differences on the hydrodynamic resistance of the supply lines, or occasional changes caused by partial clogging.

2.3 Imaging of sprays and cones

The spraying modes could be easily identified by following the current traces as well as the liquid meniscus shape at the exit of each emitter tube. The meniscus is imaged best under *brightfield* conditions, for which a LED backlight was positioned behind the emitter array, and the array was imaged from the opposite side (front view). In this case, image contrast arises from attenuation of light by the cones, while attenuation by the sprays is small. To image the spray plumes *darkfield* illumination was used, whereby image contrast arises from light scattered (rather than attenuated) by the droplets. In this case, the backlight was replaced by a black velvet cloth, which provided a dark background, while the sprays were illuminated from two white LED spot lamps positioned symmetrically at roughly 45° from the array mid plane. Additional views of the sprays were taken from a side, in order to reconstruct the directions of the micro-jets in 3D (section 3.3.2). Front view images were shot with an OLYMPUS PEN E-PL7 photo camera with a Nikkor macro lens (60 mm, 1:2.8). Side images were taken with an OLYMPUS PEN EP-1 photo camera and a ZUIKO 14-42 mm zoom lens. Most of the images we show later are enhanced for brightness and contrast, while some are presented with their tone scale inverted ("negative images") to better show the spray outline.

2.4 Spraying protocol

Electrospraying was carried in laboratory air, whose temperature (T) and relative humidity (between 35% and 64% for all the experiments) was determined with a Vaisala HM34 meter. A typical experimental run starts with setting the gas pressure to achieve the desired flow rate. Some minutes are required for the pressure to stabilize and for the liquid to fill the lines. Once the flow rate is steady, the data acquisition is initiated, and the applied voltage is ramped-up manually, and pictures are shot frequently. The main spraying modes which we differentiate in the experiments described are the *intermittent cone-jet* and the *steady cone-jet* modes (Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018). The former one, also known as *pulsating mode* (Smith, 1986; Bober & Chen, 2011), is characterized by a lower current level, and is encountered before the steady mode, as voltage is increased. Fig. 2 shows several transitions between the two modes, triggered by small adjustments of the collector voltage.

Fig. 2. Collected raw data from an example run with a 5-emitter array. The currents are represented by symbols of the kind I_i , where i is the emitter index with 0 referring to the central emitter. The collector voltage V_c was varied manually. The gauge pressure P_g is proportional to the liquid flow rate.

Table 2 - Solute concentrations and electrical conductivities of ethylene glycol solutions.

Solution code	Solutes and nominal mass fractions	Electrical conductivity, S/m
SC025	NaCl 0.0025%	4.2×10^{-4} (at 22.8 °C)
SC027	NaCl 0.0027%	2.9×10^{-4} (at 20.6 °C)
SC250	NaCl 0.0250%	2.3×10^{-3} (at 24.9 °C)
SC900	NaCl 0.0900%	1.1×10^{-2} (at 21.5 °C)
AW	Acetic acid 1.900% Water 3.610%	3.8×10^{-4} (at 21.6 °C)

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Electric field computations

Our experimental array geometries include a backplate, which is a conducting plate located behind the emitters, which are at the same electric potential as the backplate. The two plates (backplate and collector) define a parallel-capacitor gap, which hosts the linear array of emitters and sprays, and shields them from external perturbations. To find out whether dense linear arrays of Taylor cones are scalable without bound, we have investigated how the electric field scales with the number of operated emitters. "Dense" here means that the separation between the emitters' tips and the collector is large compared to the spacing between emitters (pitch). Since we aim to gather physical insights, our numerical computations are for simplified systems: The field due to a linear array of lines-of-charge, which emulate the space charge of electrosprays (section 3.1.1), and the field in an array of emitters without space charge (section 3.1.2). A similar line-of-charge approximation has been used previously to analyze the behavior of finite 2D arrays of electrosprays by Deng & Gomez (2007). They showed that this model correctly predicts the minimum driving field necessary to operate the array. In addition, they correctly predict the outlines of the spray plumes of both the main and satellite droplets for a single electro spray.

3.1.1 Electric field scaling due to space charge (lines-of-charge)

We start by asking how the electric field strength grows as more lines-of-charge (space charge) are added in the capacitor gap. The presence of emitters is omitted in this system, akin to an array of sprays emitted from an extractor plate. In our simplified system, each line-of-charge is straight, joining the two conducting parallel plates, and has uniform charge density λ (C/m). The plates are of infinite extent, so we can use the *method of images* to solve the electrostatics problem (Jackson, 1998). In our computation, we assume no voltage difference between the two plates. Fig. 3a shows the first few of the infinite series of image charges of a single line-of-charge. The electric field due to the line-of-charge and its first J image lines-of-charge pairs computed at the mid plane between the plates and at a distance x from the line has modulus

$$E_x(x; J) = \frac{\lambda}{4\pi\epsilon_0 H} \frac{2H}{x} \left\{ \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{2x}{H}\right)^2 + 1}} + \sum_{j=1}^J (-1)^j \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{2x}{H}\right)^2 + 1}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{2x}{H}\right)^2 + 1}} \right] \right\} \quad (1)$$

Here, ϵ_0 is the electric permittivity of vacuum, and H is the separation between the plates. The first term inside {...} is the contribution due to the real line-of-charge while the summation over index j is due to its

image-charges. This summation must be solved numerically but converges rapidly as J increases (Fig. 3b). To be on the safe side, we have used $J = 1000$ in all remaining computations.

Next, we have used this equation to compute the electric field modulus due to a linear array of lines-of-charge, at the array edge and the mid-plane between the plates (Fig. 4a): $E_T = \sum_{i=2}^N E_{xi}$, where i is the line index, N is the number of lines, and E_{xi} is given by equation (1), where x are the distances from each line i to line 1 (where the field is computed), $x = (i - 1)P$. Fig. 4b shows how the field modulus at the edge of the array increases as an array is expanded by adding lines, thus increasing the array width W . At values of W comparable to H , the field modulus (data set labelled "total" in Fig. 4b) asymptotes out rapidly. This trend is much slower if only the real charges are considered. Therefore, the image charge lines accelerate the convergence. In other words, the electric field due to a line-of-charge becomes strongly shielded by the two plates at distances from the line which are farther than about H . This picture holds true for other line densities as shown in Fig. 4c. In fact, the approach toward the asymptote becomes faster for denser arrays (smaller pitch P). As a corollary, in a long array, the electric field strength due to the space charge (lines-of-charge) is nearly zero everywhere except within a distance of about H from the array edge. A similar picture arises in 2D (square $N \times N$) arrays of lines-of-charge between two parallel plates, although the electric field strength is greater, as expected (see Fig. 4d).

The line-of-charge model assumes that the lines are straight despite the interaction among the sprays. This is obviously only an approximation, which does not predict the deflections of the lines. However, in the parallel plate geometry, the model predicts that the interactions felt by any line arise mostly from its neighbors in a region of influence of width H on either side. Therefore, these interactions lead to a net zero force on lines which are inside the array (far from the edge compared to H). Whereas they should result in a net force on lines near the ends of the array (within a distance from the edge of about H), resulting in increasingly large deflections of the sprays. This is confirmed by experiments, as discussed later.

Fig. 3. Electric field computation due to a single line of charge placed between two conducting infinite plates. (a) Real and image line-of-charge elements considered in the computation of E_x , the x -component of the electric field computed at the midplane between the two plates, at a distance x from the line-of-charge. (b) Effect of the number of images J considered in the computation of E_x using Eq. (1), non-dimensionalized with $E_0 \equiv \lambda/(4\pi\epsilon_0 H)$.

Fig. 4. Electric field for a linear array of N lines-of-charge lying across two parallel conducting plates, at the edge of the array. a) Geometrical parameters definition and location of the electric field whose modulus is computed. (b) Electric field modulus ("total") and contributions from the "real" charge and its "images". (c) Total electric field modulus versus non-dimensionalized array width W/H , for various array line densities H/P . (d) Total electric field modulus calculation at the corner of a square $N \times N$ array of lines-of-charge, at the mid-plane between two parallel conducting plates. The field modulus is non-dimensionalized with $E_0 \equiv \lambda/(4\pi\epsilon_0 H)$. $J = 1000$ in Eq. (1).

3.1.2 Electric field created by an array of protruding tube emitters

For an array of equally spaced emitters, the electric field at the emitters' tips intensifies towards the two ends of the array. To assess the severity of this "array-end effect" and to guide our designs of array-end passive electrodes, we have solved Laplace's equation for the electrostatic potential ϕ in a linear array of cylindrical electrodes ($\nabla^2\phi = 0$) using COMSOL Multiphysics 5.2. Space charge has been left out for simplicity. In addition, we have assessed the role played by emitter protrusion from the backplate (L). Fig. 5 shows the computational domain, taken by symmetry as 1/4 of the whole system. The backplate is

set at the same potential as the emitters, like in our experiments. The emitters are terminated with a hemisphere, resembling a pendant drop, to avoid electric field divergences caused by sharp edges (Fig. 5c). The geometrical parameters are taken from our experimental geometry.

Fig. 6a shows the electric potential ϕ along the x direction at the base of the emitters' cylindrical portion ($y = 0, z = -L$) (labelled "equator" in Fig. 5c). Minus the slope of the potential, $-d\phi/dx$, is the electric field x -component E_x . For emitters $i = 1, 2, 3$, the slope of the potential is nearly equal on the two sides of the emitter, the field becoming increasingly asymmetric as the emitters approach the array end. Fig. 6b shows the normalized field strength at the equator of the hemispherical cap *versus* the emitter's azimuth (θ_i). The two last positions ($i = 5$ and 6) "see" an electric field that is significantly stronger and azimuthally less uniform than the other emitters' positions. The near constancy of the field strength for the inner emitters is possible because D is small compared to P .

The effect from emitter protrusion (L) on the field strength is shown in Fig. 7. The strength is taken for the central emitter, although its value is similar as for others except at the array ends, as discussed earlier. The field strength increases with L as the backplate shielding reduces, and is expected to approach an asymptote for large L . In other words, the location of the backplate becomes less important as its distance from the emitters' tips becomes large compared to the emitter to collector distance (H). In practice, often one seeks to reduce the range of operating voltages, and, as predicted by these computations, we can decrease the operating voltage by increasing L , but after some L the gain is minimal.

Fig. 5. System geometry for electrostatic field computation in absence of space charge.

Fig. 6. (a) Electric potential ϕ along the line cutting through the emitters' hemispheres' equators (i.e. line $z = -L$; see Fig. 5), for a 13- and 23-emitter linear arrays, normalized by the potential difference between plates, ϕ_0 . (b) Electric field strength versus azimuth on the emitter's hemisphere's equatorial plane. The electric field strength has been non-dimensionalized with $E_{ref} = \phi_0/D$. Zero azimuth corresponds to the x direction (pointing towards edge of the array). Emitter diameter $D = 0.4$ mm, pitch $P = 2.5$ mm, emitter protrusion $L = 15$ mm, and collector distance $H = 20$ mm

Fig. 7. Electric field strength at the pole of the central emitter (see inset) as a function of emitter protrusion from the backplate L , in a 13-emitter linear array as shown in figure 5. Emitter diameter $D = 0.4$ mm, pitch $P = 2.5$ mm, collector distance $H = 10$ mm. The electric field strength is non-dimensionalized using $E_{ref} = \phi_0/D$.

3.2 Designs of electrodes at the array ends and their electrostatic influence on Taylor cones

The numerical simulations in the previous section tell us that linear arrays of electrosprays can be scaled up without bound when using the parallel-plate geometry, while distortions of the electrostatic field are confined to the array extremes. Encouraged by this conclusion, we have implemented real linear arrays and studied their behavior. The previous computations advise the use of the parallel plate geometry to obtain fast electrostatic shielding of the space charge (sec. 3.1.1). In addition, they advise using non-spraying emitter-like electrodes at the ends of the array, which we refer to as *end-electrodes* or *array-end electrodes*. Previous works (Rulison & Flagan, 1993; Quang Tran et al., 2010; Tan et al., 2017) have used a single passive emitter (dummy nozzle) at each end of a linear array. We, on the other hand, consider a *pair* of end-electrodes at each end. Table 3 shows the parameters for the array configurations used in this study.

Table 3 - Array configurations used in this work (wherein the number of emitters is not reported, as it is considered adjustable for each configuration)

Parameter	Symbol	Array configuration		
		A	B	C
Emitter outer diameter (mm)	D	0.40	0.40	0.40
Emitter pitch (center-to-center separation) (mm)	P	2.5	2.5	2.5
Emitter protrusion from the back plate (mm)	L	16	10.6	23.2
Emitter to collector distance (mm)	H	13	20.4	7.9;10;13
Number of end-electrodes on each side of the array	–	2	2	2
End electrode diameter (mm)	–	0.40	0.40	0.40 and 1.2
End electrode protrusion from the emitter ends plane (mm)	–	0	1.6	0

Fig. 8 shows three of the end-electrodes configurations that we have tested. The end-electrodes are non-spraying and are marked with a *. Although the arrays differ in the number of emitters, this is immaterial for the present discussion. The first design, configuration A, comprises two pairs of passive emitters (also called "dummy nozzles" and "blind nozzles" in the literature) coplanar with the emitters. In

configuration B, the four passive emitters protrude from the emitters' exit plane, and this helps straighten the outermost Taylor cones, relative to configuration A, where they were bent outwards. (Protrusion of a single passive electrode on each side was previously proposed by Hubacz & Marijnisen, 2003). In configurations A and B, our system was prone to electric discharges under large voltages in air. To address this issue, a new configuration C was developed in which the outermost end-electrode is a fat cylinder terminated in a large spheroid. It is made by inserting a metal head pin into a snug-fitting metal capillary tubing, itself being inserted on a passive emitter. Note that imperfections in positioning and geometry for the passive emitters in Configuration A (more obvious on the right side) do not result in appreciable differences in the inclination of the two extreme Taylor cones.

As shown in Fig. 7, the field strength decreases rapidly with L , as L becomes smaller than H . Therefore, in all the arrays considered here, the emitter protrudes from the backplate by a greater distance than the emitter to collector distance: $L/H > 1$. In this way, the electric field at the emitters' tips is strong enough to electro spray at relatively low voltage.

Fig. 8. Configurations of array-end electrodes used in this study. Such electrodes are marked with a *, while the spraying emitters show Taylor cones. Note that the configuration letter (A, B, C) does not identify the number of spraying emitters, and corresponds to the configurations in Table 3. The thin end-electrodes are passive (non-spraying) emitters.

Fig. 9 shows that the Taylor cones' lengths and cone angles are quite sensitive to changes in voltage, while their individual currents are nearly the same. The reason for this is as follows: If the applied voltage (absolute value) is suddenly reduced while liquid is continuously (and independently) supplied through each emitter, the rate at which liquid flows out of each cone through its microjet must decrease. Consequently, the Taylor cone volume increases, thus elongating. At the same time, as the cone angle decreases, the field strength in the microjet region increases, resulting in increased flow in that region

(Fernandez de la Mora, 1992). Eventually, the steady-flow condition is restored when the liquid flow rate supplied into the cone equates that at which the liquid flows out through the microjet.

Accordingly, the Taylor cones have different lengths along the array because the electrical fields around each of them have different strengths. Therefore, one can assess such electric field strength differences by comparing the differences in cone length and seeing how much V_c must change for a reference cone (e.g. the center cone) to experience the same changes. In panel (c) of Fig. 9 the cone length difference between the array-end cones and the center cone is less than that experienced by the center cone (reference) between panel (c) (-4.95 kV) and panel (b) (-5.16 kV), a 4.2% change. Therefore, the field strength differences between the array-end cones and the center cone must be in the order of only a few %, probably less than 4.2%.

This small difference in electrical field has no significant effects on the droplets: Slightly different starting positions relative to the emitter, and slightly different initial acceleration. The droplet size and charge (thus electrical current) is known to be largely unaffected by changes in the Taylor cone shape (e.g. length) or orientation (tilting), so long as the liquid flow rate is independently controlled and is kept constant for all the emitters (Fernandez de la Mora & Loscertales, 1993; Rosell-Llompart & Fernandez de la Mora, 1994; Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018). Therefore, near constancy in electrical current at a given flow rate can be taken as a reliable indicator of near constancy in the droplets' properties. As proof of constant droplet size, we report ancillary experiments in Fig. 10 using a polymeric solute to create particles from the droplets in a 7-emitter array. The particle size histograms associated to distinct emitters are similar (Fig. 10b).

Emitter wetting is an important effect related to the above discussion. Wetting of the emitter side walls by the liquid would enlarge the Taylor cone, thus weakening the field strength at the tip of the cone (by electrostatic shielding). As a result, the cone-jet mode could cease to be stable. In our system, such wetting does not take place due to the high surface tension of our solvent (~47 mN/m for MEG), permitting more uniform field conditions and robust spraying. Wetting would be more likely by organic solvents with low surface tension, as are sometimes used for particle production (such as dichloromethane; acetone, chloroform, which lie below 30 mN/m), and this issue would have to be addressed in the design, even if extractor electrodes were used.

Fig. 9. Effect of applied voltage on Taylor cone elongation, in 11-emitter array with configuration C (Table 3). Flow rate per emitter of $1.58 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$; $T = 23.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; solution SC025. The dotted line shows the center of the array for reference. Values below the Taylor cones refer to the time-averaged electrical current in nA measured on each emitter.

Fig. 10. Ancillary experiments by electrospinning a polymer solution, to test uniformity of spraying across the array. (a) Ethyl cellulose particle deposition spots with scanning electron micrographs of the particle collections from three spots (center of spot), and (b) corresponding histograms of particle sizes.

Experiment information: Solution is 1% w/v ethyl cellulose (4cP viscosity, 48% ethoxy content) and 0.0004% w/v rhodamine in butanone; 7-emitter array with end-electrode configuration A ($D = 0.4 \text{ mm}$, $P = 2.5 \text{ mm}$, $H = 20 \text{ mm}$, $L = 11 \text{ mm}$), spraying into nitrogen with $T = 29.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} < 20\%$; flow rate per emitter of $1.5 \mu\text{l}/\text{min}$.

3.3 Spray plume patterns in the steady cone-jet mode

We have studied how the spray plumes in steady cone-jet mode are influenced by the presence of other spray plumes, and how they evolve with voltage. We also demonstrate the importance of complementing 2D planar imaging with stereoscopic imaging for interpreting the spray plume patterns correctly. First, we compare the plume patterns in the steady and intermittent cone-jet spraying modes. The steady cone-jet mode is characterized by a stationary spray and stationary meniscus in the shape of a Taylor cone-jet, while the intermittent cone-jet mode appears when the tip of the meniscus oscillates rapidly, resulting in intermittent sprays. The frequency of the intermittency is usually too high to be perceived, unless a high-speed camera or a fast photodetector is used, but the two modes can be easily distinguished by the meniscus appearance (Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018) and by the current traces. Fig. 11 shows an array in which some emitters (positions -1 to +4, indicated by an arrow) undergo a transition from the intermittent cone-jet mode (in panel a)) to the steady cone-jet mode (in panel b)) when the voltage is increased at constant flow rate. In the transition, the spray plumes become significantly narrower because, compared to the intermittent mode, the specific charge on the droplets increases. Therefore, they attain higher velocity in the field, thus requiring a longer distance to lose their inertia and start moving electrophoretically (of order $V_0 \times \tau$, where V_0 is the initial speed and τ is the droplet dynamic relaxation time; Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018). On losing their inertia, the droplets are seeded into more "centrally" located electrophoretic paths than in the intermittent mode case, leading to a narrower plume spread. The figure also shows that in the intermittent mode the sprays overlap at the edges, while sprays in the stable cone-jet mode are clearly separated. The crossing of different electrophoretic trajectories in the steady state is forbidden for a mono-mobile charged aerosol (since the droplets' velocity vector equals the sum of the gas velocity vector and the product of electric field vector times the droplet's electrical mobility -constant for a mono-mobile aerosol-, and both of these vectors are uniquely defined in space). Therefore, the overlapping of the intermittent sprays is either due to sprays falling on different planes (more likely) or due to intermittent changes in the electric field recorded in the single long-exposure image (less likely).

This experiment also shows differences in the repulsion between the sprays in the different modes. The sprays in positions -2 and +5, are clearly re-oriented (repelled more) after the transition, reflecting that the space charge in the space occupied by sprays -1 to +4 has increased when they go from intermittent to steady cone-jet mode. On the other hand, the sprays in cone-jet mode in positions -5, -4, -3 are virtually identical before and after the transition.

3.3.1 Spray patterns uniformity near minimum voltage

Based on the calculations from section 3.1, we would expect to find two distinct regions in a very long linear array of electrospray emitters (at least, in the backplate-and-collector "condenser" configuration, considered here): An "inner" region, in which the sprays are unaffected by the actual length of the array,

and two "outer" regions, located at either end of the array, where "end effects" are concentrated. This is the result of the fact that the electrostatic repulsion from faraway sprays do not amount to a relevant force. To check whether this picture holds, we have determined the sizes of these regions by following the evolution of the spray plumes as a function of the number of operated emitters, N_{on} , in a given array with N emitters ($N \geq N_{on}$). The comparison is made at near the "onset voltage" V_{up} condition, namely at

Fig. 11. Difference in appearance of electro spray plumes from intermittent and steady modes. a) The arrows indicate the emitters in the intermittent cone-jet mode where $V_c = -6.3$ kV ($I_{avg} = 84$ nA). b) All the emitters are in the steady cone-jet mode at collector voltage of -6.7 kV, ($I_{avg} = 123$ nA). Array configuration C, flow rate per emitter $Q = 0.5$ μ L/min, solution SC900, distance from emitter tip to collector $H = 8.3$ mm, $P = 2.5$ mm and $T = 21.9$ $^{\circ}$ C. These images were obtained from darkfield photographs after inverting the tone scale. The star shapes on at the tips of emitters -3 and -2 in panel a), -1 to +2 in panel b) are lens flares produced by bright reflections of the illumination source on these emitters; they are not related to the liquid atomization.

the applied voltage for which all the emitters in the array have attained the steady cone-jet mode from the intermittent mode. The recorded individual current traces have allowed us to accurately pinpoint these voltages. Fig. 12 shows the evolution as N_{on} grows from 1 (starting at the center emitter) to the emitter number N , for two arrays, with $N = 7$ and 11. At each condition the voltage is the one at which the *last* emitter in the array has stabilized into the steady cone-jet mode. Note that this voltage increases as N_{on} grows, probably due to increased space charge. Similarly, the voltages in Fig. 12b are comparatively higher than in Fig. 12a for an equal number of operating sprays, and this can be attributed to the larger liquid conductivity (K) for Fig. 12b causing increased space charge.

The plumes geometry is symmetric about the central emitter (position $i=0$). The plumes are clearly separated (i.e., do not overlap), while the spray plume widths increase with emitter index i . For both

arrays (Fig. 12) the central plume ($i=0$) gets narrower as N_{on} increases from 1 to 3, and from 3 to 5, but does not change appreciably from 5 to 7, and so on from 7 to 9, and to 11 in the larger array (Fig. 12b). Similar trends are observed with the next emitter positions, $i = +1, -1$, as their circumstance changes from being at the array edge to being in the "inner region" of the array. We observe that the "edge region" of the array defined above appears to occupy one or at most two sprays at either end of the array.

Fig. 12. Evolution of the spray pattern as a function of the number of operated emitters when the voltage is near the onset value (V_{up}) in a 2.5 mm pitch array of a) 7 emitters, and b) 11 emitters. Conditions: (a) Solution = AW, end electrode configuration A, $H = 13$ mm, $L = 16$ mm, $Q = 0.76$ $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. (b) solution = SC250, end electrode configuration C, $H = 10$ mm, $L = 23$ mm, $Q = 1.3$ $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$. Common to (a) and (b): $P = 2.5$ mm. The vertical lines visible on the (a) panels are reflections of the light source on the emitters. Inverted grey tone brightfield images. Q and I are the average per emitter. I is not available for the 7-emitter array runs. Some liquid accumulation is visible in panels (a).

3.3.2 Symmetry breaking at high voltages

At high enough values of the applied voltage (raised at fixed liquid flow rate), the Taylor cones bend away from the emitter axis. Meanwhile, the sprays adopt asymmetric static shapes, as shown in Fig. 13. At this condition, the cones retract, becoming small and difficult to visualize; while the light scattered from the various sprays differs in intensity despite being in the same mode. For these reasons, the individual current traces can be a useful tool for identifying the cone-jet mode.

As discussed in section 3.2, when the voltage is raised at constant flow rate, the Taylor cone-jet momentarily experiences an increased electric pull, and the cone becomes shorter ("retracts" towards the capillary). Simultaneously, since the droplets' speeds increase (while the droplet mobility is not significantly affected), the spray space charge is reduced, hence reinforcing the field strength in the cone-jet region. On further increases in applied voltage, the cone-jet retracts further, but eventually must tilt. Tilting of the Taylor cone is a familiar phenomenon in conventional electrospraying from single emitters without extractor. Yet to our knowledge the underlying mechanism has not been discussed in the literature. We know that the specific direction of the jetting is repeatable in each experiment, but we ignore what determines it. We may list as potential factors: (i) imperfections in the emitter leading to asymmetries in the liquid flow, and (ii) asymmetries in the electric field surrounding the Taylor cone (the so called "far field"). Category (i) includes both imperfections at inner emitter surfaces which can induce asymmetric hydrodynamics, and different outer emitter morphology and/or composition which can induce non-symmetric wetting conditions, influencing the contact line. The use of a linear array allows us to probe into the role of category-(ii) factors, i.e. the asymmetries in the electric field. We can see in Fig. 6b that the electric field is slightly more intense on the two "exposed" sides of the emitter (angles $\pm\pi/2$) than on its "within array" sides (angles 0 and π). In addition, emitters closer to the array edge experience stronger field (Fig. 6a and b). Finally, the field may be influenced by emitter misalignment.

We have used stereoscopic imaging to determine the direction at which each of the jets aims, as shown in Figs. 14. The array was not perturbed between the two experiments; the only difference in configuration being the height of the emitter ends relative to the collector plate (H). Panels (a) and (b) show the front and rotated views of the sprays. These images are used to determine the $(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)$ location of a point on the jet relative to the center of the tip of its emitter. The point on the jet is chosen in all cases to be relatively far downstream from the Taylor cone, near the end of the straight section of the jet, before it "flares out" as a spray. Therefore, it may be located downstream the actual jet breakup point. These "jet" coordinates are then plotted with the (x, y) positions of the emitters in the top views of panel (c). The emitters' coordinates are independently obtained from a bottom view photo of the emitter array taken in absence of liquid and voltage (not shown), obtained by means of a mirror at 45° from the camera's optical axis. A rotated view of a low voltage condition for which the sprays are straight is provided in Fig. 14d for comparison. Fig. 15 shows another case.

Comparing panels (c) between Figs. 14 and 15, we find that the jets' positions relative to the emitters are very similar with only one exception ($i = -4$), and that they do not follow any symmetric pattern about the central emitter. To understand how the jets "choose" a particular direction, it helps to analyze each side of the array separately. On the left side, the emitters' misalignments and jet directions follow a zig-zag pattern (except for the end emitter, $i = -5$, in Fig. 14), and are correlated. The jets' are deflected toward the same side as their emitter misalignment in the y -direction. This suggests that the emitters' misalignments distort the electric field sufficiently. On the right side of the array, the emitters are aligned better, and this may explain why there is no zig-zag pattern in this case, as their jets mostly aim toward one side of the array ($y < 0$). Therefore, other factors are at play. This experiment does not resolve what these factors are, but may be related to the emitter geometry, as mentioned earlier, or wetting. That the electric field is not the sole factor can be seen by the fact that many jets point toward the array center, while the electric field should be pointing outward (see section 3.1.1).

Fig. 13. Composition of a bright-field image (top) and the tone inverted dark-field image (bottom) of the linear array. Parameters $V_c = 9.17$ kV, $H = 10$ mm, solution= SC250, $T = 27.1$ °C, $Q = 0.6$ μ l/min, $I = 99.5$ nA (Q and I are per emitter.).

Fig. 14. Stereoscopic reconstruction of the azimuthal angle of the cone-jet in a high voltage situation for 11-emitters array ($P = 2.5$ mm, $H = 7.9$ mm). a) Front view. b) View rotated to the right (by 74° off the front-view optical axis). c) x - y positions of the emitters (circles) and the microjets (crosses) (see text). $Q = 0.6$ μ l/min, $V_c = -8.39$ kV, $I = 79$ nA, $T = 24^\circ$ C, solution = SC250. d) Rotated view of a lower voltage condition, shown for comparison ($V_c = 6.2$ kV, $I = 83$ nA, other parameters being the same as for b)). (Q and I are per emitter.)

Fig. 15. Stereoscopic reconstruction of the azimuthal angle of the cone-jet in a high voltage situation for 9-emitters array ($P = 2.5$ mm, $H = 10$ mm). a) Front view. b) View rotated to the right (by 61° off the front-view optical axis). c) x - y positions of emitters (circles) and the microjets (crosses) (see text). $Q = 0.5$ μ l/min, $V_c = 7,23$ kV, $I = 82$ nA, $T = 28^\circ$ C, solution = SC250.

3.4 Cone-jet mode transitions near the onset voltage

The transition from intermittent to steady spraying happens at a critical condition of the electric field acting on the liquid in the Taylor cone region. The changes in spraying mode can be identified for each emitter as jumps in current (see Fig. 2). This capability has allowed us to investigate how uniform the electric field stays along the array, for different arrays and operating conditions. In addition, we address whether the electric field in the central region of the array becomes bounded as the number of operated sprays is increased as done in Fig. 12.

3.4.1 Taylor cones stabilization and destabilization sequences within the array

Using the 11-emitter array with end-electrode configuration C, we have studied the order in which the spraying stabilizes in the cone-jet mode for each emitter in the array, as the applied voltage is raised, and as a function of the number of emitters being operated, N_{on} . These configurations always include the center emitter, and N_{on} attains values 1, 3, 5, ...11. For each configuration, we have scanned the collector voltage to determine V_{up} , the *onset voltage* for the steady cone-jet spraying at each emitter, and once all of the emitters are in steady cone-jet mode we have lowered the voltage to determine, V_{down} , the *minimum voltage* at which the steady cone-jet mode is no longer be sustained and the intermittent mode sets in. V_{up} and V_{down} do not coincide, due to a hysteresis well known for individual emitters (Smith, 1986). For convenience we refer to positive voltage values, i.e. minus the collector voltage values.

Fig. 16 shows the V_{up} versus emitter position for different combinations of spraying-emitter number N_{on} , flow rate per emitter Q , and emitter-to-collector distances H . We find that the onset voltage at each position in the array increases with N_{on} and with Q . This result implies that the spray electric charge (space charge), which increases with these parameters, influences the electric field strength at the Taylor cones. As more sprays are turned on, the repulsive force exerted by the sprays on the Taylor cones increases, thus weakening the electric field in that region, which must be overcome by an increment in the voltage to achieve enough field strength to sustain a stable Taylor cone. However, for the centrally located emitters ($i = 0$ and ± 1), this effect weakens or disappears as the number of sprays becomes large enough. For them, the onset voltage tends to a plateau value. When the plateau condition is approached by an emitter, the repulsive forces from the additional sprays contribute negligibly to the weakening of the field at the emitter in question. These observations confirm the existence of two kinds of regions in long arrays, an inner region and two outer regions near the array edges.

We also confirm that the electric field is stronger near the edges of the array, since this is where the transition to the steady cone-jet mode is met first. (Note that the voltage differences between array center and edge would get wider if the passive end-electrodes were absent, possibly even preventing

stabilization of the entire array.) The electric potential difference at the mode transition depends on any factors influencing the electric field, including the geometry of the electrodes and the presence of space charge. Therefore, in a linear array *without* extractor plate such as ours, it is not surprising to detect this transition at different voltage values for different emitter positions.

The role played by space charge is revealed also in the transient behavior of the sprays at the voltages preceding complete stability, while still some of the sprays are in the intermittent mode. In this "transient regime" sprays flip-flop transiently into and out of the cone-jet mode. As one spray in intermittent mode becomes stable, a neighboring spray already in that mode will feel a decrease in field strength due to the increased space charge, and may therefore revert to the intermittent cone-jet mode. Such cross-talk between sprays is more pronounced at large Q and H (due to the increased space charge), revealed in more frequent "flickering" of the sprays, and the sudden global stabilization of the array when a critical value of the voltage was reached. This is the case for $Q = 1.9 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and $H = 10 \text{ mm}$ at which V_{up} is flat across much of the array (Fig. 16).

Figure 17 shows the onset voltage at which all the emitters have stabilized for a given Q , as a function of number of operated emitters, at three different H . This onset voltage tends towards a plateau as expected from the trends observed in Fig. 16. For collector distance H of 13 mm, at high enough voltage a corona and in some cases, spark discharges were audible. Although these took place at some unknown location on the collector electrode edges, they interfered with the current measuring equipment. Therefore, as a precaution, for these experiments the current data acquisition was disconnected, and the mode transitions were identified by changes in the Taylor cones and the spray plumes. However, no gaseous discharges were present for the data points shown.

Fig. 18 shows V_{down} for similar parameters. We would expect to find similar trends as for V_{up} except for a space-charge dependent shift in the transition voltages, responsible for the well-known hysteresis mentioned earlier. The transition is observed sooner (i.e. at higher voltage) in the central emitters, where the field is weaker and the Taylor cones are more elongated (Fig. 9c), than at the outer emitters, where the field is strongest. Unlike for V_{up} , we do not find for V_{down} in Fig. 18 a monotonous dependence on the number of operated emitters. Here too, we observe in some cases that the transition of a single spray causes the destabilization of neighboring sprays in cascade, resulting in the flat portions of the curves shown in Fig. 18. In this case, destabilization in one spray leads to reduced space charge, and therefore the field strength intensifies at nearby spraying emitters. However, instead of reinforcing the steady cone jet mode, the sudden intensification of the electric field causes destabilization. Perhaps such sudden perturbations result in the emission of a large fragment from the meniscus causing a drop in the field at the liquid meniscus, which then transitions into the intermittent cone-jet.

Fig. 16. Stabilization sequence into the cone-jet mode for the 11-emitter array, as minus the collector voltage is slowly increased, for different H and Q values. The graphs show the voltage (minus voltage applied on the collector plate) at which each emitter transitioned into the steady cone-jet mode (V_{up}) versus emitter position i . Liquid= SC250, configuration C. Q is the flow rate per emitter.

Fig. 17. Onset voltage for the 11-emitter array versus number of operated emitters at different emitter to collector separations. The flow rate is the same for all ($1.35 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$).

Fig. 18. Destabilization sequence from the cone-jet mode for the 11-emitter array, as minus the collector voltage is slowly decreased, for different H and Q values. The graphs show the voltage (minus voltage applied on the collector plate) at which each emitter transitioned from the steady cone-jet mode to the intermittent cone-jet mode (V_{down}) versus emitter position i . Liquid= SC250, configuration C. Q is the flow rate per emitter.

An interesting qualitative observation is that the array can be stabilized at a lower voltage than V_{up} . While the array is operating in the intermittent cone-jet, at a voltage a few hundred volts lower than V_{up} (but larger than V_{down}), a sudden gush of air is directed towards it, strong enough to blow the sprays away from under the emitters. The array recovers itself directly into the steady cone-jet mode (see complementary video data). We believe that the space charge below the emitters was momentarily carried away, causing the local field at the tip of the emitters to reach the required value to enter the stable cone-jet mode stability region. Due to hysteresis, the array remains stable (Smith, 1986; Cloupeau and Prunet-Foch, 1989).

3.4.2 Role of electrical conductivity (K) on the onset voltage (V_{up})

The role of space charge also becomes apparent when changing the electrical conductivity of the liquid, K . When K is reduced, the transition voltage V_{up} from intermittent to steady spraying is reduced significantly. This is shown in Fig. 19 for the 11-emitter array, which compares data obtained with liquids differing in K by a factor of ~ 8 . The comparison is made at equal flow rate per emitter (Q) and emitter-collector separation (H). In Fig. 19b, we observe similar patterns of the emitter transition voltage for the two K values, except for the shift to lower voltages as K is decreased. Fig. 20 shows that the plume configurations obtained with these liquids are strikingly different.

We interpret the reduction in V_{up} when K is decreased as caused by differences in the spray space charge. The electric field required to sustain the Taylor cones should be nearly the same for both liquids, as their surface tensions are similar. However, the contribution from the space charge to this electrical field is different depending on K , being lower for the low- K liquid. This is due both to the lower amount of charge, and the fact that it is distributed farther away (Fig. 20). Order of magnitude analysis considering charge conservation under steady state shows that the electrical charge contained in a spray is proportional to the electrical current and inversely proportional to the applied voltage and the electrical mobility of the droplets. The reduction in K causes a decrease in electrical current (per emitter) from 149 to 43.7 nA, a factor of about 3.4, which is close to the square root of the electrical conductivity values (2.8), in approximate agreement with scaling laws proposed in the literature (Fernandez de la Mora & Loscertales, 1994; Gañán-Calvo et al., 1997; Rosell-Llompart et al., 2018). The electrical mobility of the droplets can be compared for the two conductivities considering the scaling laws of droplet charge and size, resulting in larger mobility for the low K case. Both of these effects lead to higher space charge for the larger K case, despite the difference in applied voltage.

Fig. 19. Effect of liquid electrical conductivity for a 11-emitter array, (a) on the transition voltage V_{up} versus number of operated emitters, and (b) V_{up} versus emitter position i in the array. Parameters: $Q = 1.35 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ (per emitter), $H = 10$ mm, $P = 2.5$ mm and end electrode configuration C. Reported conductivities are from Table 2. For (b) the current per emitter was approximately uniform along the array, with mean values of 149 nA for the high conductivity liquid (SC250) at 27 °C, and 43.7 nA for the low conductivity liquid (SC025) at 24.5 °C.

a. 2.3×10^{-3} S/m

b. 2.9×10^{-4} S/m

Fig. 20. Effect of conductivity on the electrospray plume shapes, for the same flow rate per emitter (1.35 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$) and array geometry (configuration C with equal emitter tip to collector distance, $H = 10$ mm). In a) the solution is SC250, with $K = 0.0023$ S/m, $V_c = -8.39$ kV, $T = 27$ °C, current per emitter $I = 149$ nA. In b) the solution is SC025, $K = 0.00029$ S/m, $V_c = -5.78$ kV, $T = 23$ °C, $I = 43.7$ nA. Images are composites of brightfield and darkfield images in graytone.

4 Conclusions

The scaling up of the electrospray process is not trivial, as it involves operating multiple Taylor cones in a small space in the presence of strong electrostatic fields. The aim of this study is to demonstrate that linear arrays of electrosprays can be operated without extractor in dense geometries. By "dense" we mean that the separation between the counter-electrode and the electrospraying emitters is large compared to the spacing between adjacent emitters (pitch). Our approach excludes the use of so-called extractor electrodes, which can compromise reliability. Another important feature of our design is a backplate, which is a conducting plate set behind the emitters and is set at their same electric potential (voltage). The two plates (collector and backplate) define a parallel-capacitor gap that hosts the linear array and sprays, and shields them from external perturbations.

First we have gained physical insights into the question of scalability from electric field computations of arrays of lines-of-charge (section 3.1). These computations have revealed that the electric field at the edge of the array does not increase indefinitely as the array grows. Instead, the field converges towards a plateau value as the number of lines increases, and such plateau is approached when the width of the array is as small as the plate's gap (H). We have shown also that image charges in the two plates speed up the convergence of the electric field. We also reach this conclusion for 2D square arrays of lines-of-charge.

Next, we have numerically solved the electric field for linear arrays of emitter tubes protruding from the backplate, in absence of space charge (sprays), to identify if array-end non-spraying electrodes are needed in the array-in-capacitor design. We have found that at the two last positions at the extremes the electric field is significantly stronger and azimuthally less uniform than at the other positions. Therefore, we have identified as optimal array configurations the ones having on either end two non-spraying electrodes, positioned at the same pitch as the spraying emitters. We have implemented experimentally several configurations. Our most robust one has a passive (non-spraying) emitter in the innermost position and a much thicker electrode in the outermost position to prevent the appearance of gas discharges at that location. We have estimated the difference in electric field strength at the Taylor cones between the central and edge spraying emitters of only a few % (section 3.2).

By acquiring the individual time traces of the electrical current transmitted through each emitter separately, we have established two voltages when the spraying mode changes at each location on the array: The *onset voltage*, reached when the steady cone-jet mode is established as the applied voltage difference is increased while in the intermittent mode, and the *minimum voltage*, the voltage when the steady cone-jet stops after the voltage difference is lowered. We have found that near the onset voltage the sprays are straight and are similarly shaped for the central locations of the array, whereas the sprays progressively expand near the edge of the array (section 3.3.1). In another experiment (section 3.4.1), we have studied the onset voltage progression as the number of operated emitters is increased in a fixed

array from 1 to 11, by turning on only the central emitter, and progressively adding adjacent emitters. We have found that the onset voltage depends on the number of operated emitters, because the spray space charge reduces the electric field in the Taylor cone region. However, the onset voltage reaches a plateau for the innermost emitters. Its value increases when the electrical conductivity is increased, as expected from the increase in space charge (section 3.4.2). We conclude from these experiments that the electrostatic field experienced by the central region of very long arrays is not dependent of how large the array is. So, the array is expandable indefinitely while the voltage is bounded, averting gas breakdown discharges. We have shown this for arrays characterized by a small pitch of 2.5 mm (4 emitters/cm) and a collector distance as large as 13 mm.

We have also reported on "symmetry breaking" of the electrosprays, observed at high enough voltage, caused by the tilting of the Taylor cones (section 3.3.2). Tilting of a Taylor cone is a familiar phenomenon in conventional electrospraying from single emitters without extractor. Here, we have used stereoscopic imaging to identify the directions at which the microjets are pointing. We have found that those directions correlate with the slight emitters' misalignments when they have a zig-zag pattern, with the jets roughly pointing in the direction of strongest field strength. In absence of a pattern, other factors are important in this phenomenon, as, sometimes, the array end sprays point inward toward the array, instead of outward where the field is most intense. These experiments suggest that symmetry breaking may be exploited to actively control the collection of the generated droplets/particles.

The interest of electrospray scale-up arises in the context of particle production and nanostructured films. Often such systems involve highly volatile, low surface tension liquids which are prone to several complications. First, the low surface tension leads to wetting of the emitter tubes. This can lead to changes in the local electrical field, which can trigger a change in the electrospray mode. Second, fast solvent evaporation from the Taylor causes solute precipitation, often leading to unsteady spraying. And third, when spraying into ambient air, ambient humidity can absorb into the Taylor cone and trigger solute precipitation if water acts as a non-solvent in the solution. The solutions in the present study have been chosen to be free of these complications, as mentioned in the introduction. However, our conclusions still apply to other more difficult chemical compositions so long as precautions are taken to prevent the complications just mentioned.

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Highlights

- Linear arrays of electrosprays can be stabilized without extractor electrode.
- Such arrays are shown to be infinitely expandable, even for narrow emitter pitch.
- New array-end electrode design creates uniform electric field for all the emitters.
- Spray plume tilting is correlated to minute out-of-line deviations of the emitters.

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